

OFF-AXIS FIBER ORIENTATION HIGH-STRAIN RATE COMPRESSION TESTING OF K-49/3501-6 KEVLAR[®]/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) was used to study the dynamic compressive properties of K-49/3501-6 KEVLAR[®]/Epoxy laminates. Both a unidirectional (UD) and a cross-ply (XP) laminate were examined. Each laminate was a 30.5 cm (12 in) square flat panel composed of 75 plies; the test specimens were approximately 0.95 cm (3/8 in) cubes. The tested fiber orientation angles were 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, and 90 degrees. Quasi-static tests were also conducted for comparison purposes. The strain rate values varied from 200 - 1100 /s. The data for the KEVLAR[®]/Epoxy composites were obtained from 120 tests for the UD laminate and 90 tests for the XP laminate. The ultimate stress of both materials shows some strain rate sensitivity in the 1-direction, with significant reductions in stress, but no rate sensitivity for other angles. The ultimate strains for both materials increase with increasing angle, but show no rate sensitivity.

KEYWORDS: dynamic material properties, high-strain-rate, Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar, KEVLAR[®] 49, 3501-6 Epoxy, off-axis, unidirectional, cross-ply

INTRODUCTION

At present, a program is underway at the University of Delaware under the Office of Naval Research sponsorship (Dr. Y.D.S. Rajapakse) that involves three tasks:

1. The high-strain-rate testing in compression and tension of various polymer matrix composite (and other) materials using the existing SHPB facility, and correlation and statistical analysis of the dynamic material properties obtained.
2. Examination of the samples tested, using optical and scanning electron microscopy to characterize the deformation and fracture processes.
3. The evaluation of the suitability of current models, such as Johnson-Cook, Ferilli-Armstrong, Steinberg-Guinan-Lund, and Bodner-Partom, to describe the strength, deformation, and failure of these materials at high-strain-rates and the modification of these models, or whenever necessary, the development of new models.

The present paper concentrates on Task 1.

The SHPB facility at the University of Delaware has been described previously in [1-6]. Kolsky [7] introduced a method for determining mechanical properties of materials at high-strain-rates using the SHPB in 1949. The method was developed based on wave propagation

theory in elastic bars and the interaction between a stress wave and a short specimen. To begin a test, a specimen is placed between two long, 1.9 cm (3/4 in) diameter Inconel bars, the “incident bar” and the “transmitted bar”, which are supported by Teflon[®] bearings. Impact is initiated by releasing nitrogen gas from a pressurized chamber. The gas propels a striker bar (supported by and riding on Teflon[®] rings) through a guiding barrel, at the end of which it strikes the incident bar. The velocity of the striker bar just prior to impact is measured using two infrared beams at the end of the barrel. At impact, the incident bar receives an elastic compressive stress wave with a specific wave velocity and a wave shape that is a function of time. When the wave reaches the incident bar/specimen interface, a portion of the incident wave is reflected back into the incident bar as a tensile wave. The remaining portion of the wave is transmitted into the specimen as a compressive wave. The wave transmitted into the specimen travels through the specimen and reaches the specimen/transmitted bar interface, where a portion of the wave is reflected back into the specimen. The rest is transmitted into the transmitted bar as a compressive wave.

Because the specimen length is short, the initial stress wave in the specimen undergoes numerous internal reflections during the test. The stress distribution in the specimen is assumed to be uniform due to these numerous reflections. In addition it is assumed that the stress waves undergo minimal dispersion, that the bars remain elastic, and that the ends of both the incident and transmitted bars in contact with the specimen remain flat. Based on the length of the striker bar, there is a characteristic time window corresponding to the duration of the stress wave. The wave pulse time window of the University of Delaware SHPB is approximately 290 microseconds. This means that the specimen must fail within 290 microseconds after the start of the tests for failure to be accurately characterized. This has not been a problem with the relatively brittle composites tested to date.

Strain gages, connected to a Fluke PM3394A recording oscilloscope, are mounted on the incident and transmitted bars, equidistant from the specimen interfaces. The oscilloscope records the strain gage's output as a voltage versus time graph. Using this data, along with the speed of the striker bar and the physical dimensions of the bars and specimens, stress versus strain curves can be generated for different strain rates. Zukas [8] has shown that for many metals, mechanical properties vary significantly with strain rate. This new data will add to what is now available for other materials. At the University of Delaware, material systems tested to date include glass/epoxy, glass/polyester, graphite/epoxy, carbon/metal matrix, and carbon/ceramic matrix, and the most recent papers regarding these materials are given in [1-6].

SAMPLE PREPARATION

The KEVLAR[®]/Epoxy composite discussed herein is a DuPont KEVLAR[®] 49 fiber with a Hercules 3501-6 epoxy matrix. The basic UD 30.5 cm (12 in) wide prepreg tape was originally manufactured by the "hi-E" Company, and stored in the freezer at the Center for Composite Materials (CCM) at the University of Delaware. Two 30.5 cm (12 in) square flat panels, each made up of 75 plies were fabricated. The nominal thickness of each panel after curing was approximately 0.95 cm (3/8 in). One panel was laid up as a UD laminate, while the other was a mid-plane symmetric, XP laminate. All specimens were then fabricated out of these panels by using a water-cooled surface grinder equipped with a thin-kerf diamond grit saw blade. All UD and XP specimens were produced from the same respective panel by orienting the primary fiber direction at the proper angle to the saw travel. Two sets of perpendicular cuts resulted in cubic samples with approximately 0.95 cm (3/8 in) sides. The

wet diamond saw produced very little delamination and smooth cut surfaces. Further improvement of the cut surfaces was accomplished by wet polishing with 600 grit SiC paper.

Previous research, [1-6], performed using the University of Delaware SHPB facility involved right circular cylinders with a length-to-diameter (L/D) ratio of approximately 1.5. Recently, a study using a graphite/epoxy composite was conducted [9] that examined both various L/D ratios from 0.5 to 2.0 as well as a comparison between square/rectangular and cylindrical specimen geometries. Within the range of variables examined in [9], no statistically significant differences could be found in the material properties determined by the testing. These results are fortuitous, as the properties of KEVLAR[®] which make it a desirable material also make it difficult to machine, particularly smooth, cylindrical, core-drilled specimens. Consequently, square/rectangular specimens were produced and used for the tests discussed herein. The decision to use a cubic geometry also made preparation of the off-angle specimens considerably easier than if they had been core drilled.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, the typical notation convention for fibrous composite materials is followed. The 1-, 2-, and 3-directions are three mutually orthogonal axes, with the 1-direction parallel to the primary fiber direction, the 2-direction perpendicular to the primary fiber direction in the transverse dimension, and the 3-direction also perpendicular to the primary fiber direction but in the thickness dimension. Theoretically, the 2- and the 3-directions are identical in a UD material, while the 1- and the 2- directions are identical in a XP material. This theoretical orthotropic symmetry has been demonstrated for the panels in this paper in [9, 10]. The off-axis angle, Θ , for this paper is defined as the angle between the axis of the SHPB and the 1-direction of the samples; therefore $\Theta = 0$ is equivalent to the 1-direction, and $\Theta = 90$ is equivalent to the 2-direction. Because of the symmetry of the XP material it was tested only at $\Theta = 0, 15, 30,$ and 45 degrees.

The fiber volume fraction (V_f) of the KEVLAR[®] used for this testing was estimated to be 41%. This calculation was based on the measured weight and volume of a selected number of samples (average density 1.324 g/cm^3), the published density of KEVLAR[®] 49 (1.44 g/cm^3 , [11]), and an unconfirmed density for the 3501-6 epoxy (1.26 g/cm^3). The V_f of the composite that was used in [11] to provide the published ultimate stress and strain data was 60% and used an unidentified epoxy matrix.

The dynamic results from the SHPB are also compared with quasi-static compression tests performed at the CCM. The quasi-static tests were performed on an Instron 1125 screw-type machine in the constant speed mode for all Θ angles. These tests used specimens with geometry identical to that for the SHPB tests, with the samples simply placed between two flat platens and compressed to failure, and the results recorded on a strip chart. The results for the UD quasi-static tests are shown in Table 1, while those for the XP are shown in Table 2. These results are the averages of three tests for each Θ . The published quasi-static ultimate stresses in [11] for a KEVLAR[®] 49/Epoxy laminate (unspecified epoxy) with $V_f = 0.60$ are 276 MPa for the 1-direction and 137.9 MPa for the 2-direction. The published quasi-static ultimate strains in [11] for the same material are approximately 1.33% for the 1-direction and 3.11% for the 2-direction. Additionally, quasi-static compression data for the 3501-6 epoxy using an IITRI fixture has been given in [12]. The values given in [12] for ultimate stress and strain are approximately 81 MPa and 2.05% respectively. The stress-strain relation for the

3501-6 epoxy was found to be non-linear. The published comparison data from [11] and [12] are also included in Figs. 2 and 3.

Table 1: UD Quasi-Static Test Results

Θ (deg. from 1-dir)		Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
0	Average		0.0496	240.29
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0009	10.35
	Coeff. of Var.		1.90%	4.31%
15	Average		0.0530	224.23
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0027	3.79
	Coeff. of Var.		5.04%	1.69%
30	Average		0.0563	157.02
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0004	1.97
	Coeff. of Var.		0.66%	1.25%
45	Average		0.0627	130.25
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0023	1.24
	Coeff. of Var.		3.61%	0.95%
60	Average		0.0604	109.58
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0026	3.22
	Coeff. of Var.		4.29%	2.94%
75	Average		0.0521	100.94
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0003	1.35
	Coeff. of Var.		0.65%	1.34%
90	Average		0.0493	90.55
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0000	2.59
	Coeff. of Var.		0.05%	2.86%

Table 2: XP Quasi-Static Test Results

Θ (deg. from 1-dir)		Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
0	Average		0.0985	191.05
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0017	0.49
	Coeff. of Var.		1.74%	0.26%
15	Average		0.0884	167.53
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0049	9.47
	Coeff. of Var.		5.56%	5.66%
30	Average		0.1014	150.85
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0156	2.33
	Coeff. of Var.		15.35%	1.55%
45	Average		0.1521	142.00
	Std. Dev.	Quasi-static	0.0036	3.25
	Coeff. of Var.		2.39%	2.29%

The averaged dynamic test results are given in Tables 3-13. Each average value represents from three to five repeated tests at each test condition. A single test condition consisted of a specific combination of: UD or XP lay-up; fiber orientation angle, Θ (0 - 90 in 15 deg increments); and applied SHPB pressure. The applied pressure was held approximately constant for each test series (denoted by each average value) in an attempt to control the strain rate achieved in the specimen to a specific level. Within each test series, fluctuations did occur for various reasons in the applied pressure and/or the achieved strain rate. Because of this, standard deviations and coefficients of variation are given in these tables for each test series. An example of a typical stress-strain plot, developed from the recorded strain gage data, for the UD material at $\Theta = 15$ degrees and an average strain rate of 436 /sec is given in Fig. 1.

Figure 2: Example Stress-Strain Plot for the UD Material

Table 3: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 0$

$\Theta = 0$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	187.82	0.01633	294.23
Std. Dev.	28.05	0.00179	15.31
Coeff. of Var.	14.93%	10.98%	5.20%
Average	379.74	0.0071	238.48
Std. Dev.	17.05	0.0005	29.69
Coeff. of Var.	4.49%	7.05%	12.45%
Average	433.36	0.01199	315.12
Std. Dev.	15.00	0.00023	8.01
Coeff. of Var.	3.46%	1.92%	2.54%
Average	489.25	0.0128	306.97
Std. Dev.	21.63	0.0003	3.82
Coeff. of Var.	4.42%	2.15%	1.25%
Average	553.02	0.0137	314.68
Std. Dev.	43.29	0.0012	3.97
Coeff. of Var.	7.83%	8.41%	1.26%
Average	549.02	0.0142	294.34
Std. Dev.	24.00	0.0013	10.52
Coeff. of Var.	4.37%	9.13%	3.57%

Table 4: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 15$

$\Theta = 15$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	318.06	0.0121	186.72
Std. Dev.	23.84	0.0007	11.04
Coeff. of Var.	7.50%	5.46%	5.91%
Average	436.40	0.0120	204.22
Std. Dev.	14.13	0.0002	1.93
Coeff. of Var.	3.24%	1.61%	0.95%
Average	517.83	0.0124	190.60
Std. Dev.	10.83	0.0004	10.50
Coeff. of Var.	2.09%	3.53%	5.51%
Average	550.15	0.0129	189.05
Std. Dev.	64.26	0.0002	7.85
Coeff. of Var.	11.68%	1.73%	4.15%
Average	578.25	0.0133	163.01
Std. Dev.	19.25	0.0004	31.46
Coeff. of Var.	3.33%	2.85%	19.30%

Table 5: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 30$

$\Theta = 30$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	392.50	0.0191	121.39
Std. Dev.	13.75	0.0009	6.60
Coeff. of Var.	3.50%	4.72%	5.44%
Average	592.10	0.0181	108.00
Std. Dev.	72.92	0.0009	39.14
Coeff. of Var.	12.32%	4.92%	36.24%
Average	674.95	0.0181	118.90
Std. Dev.	33.91	0.0004	10.52
Coeff. of Var.	5.02%	2.13%	8.85%
Average	716.33	0.0182	124.58
Std. Dev.	38.61	0.0007	7.33
Coeff. of Var.	5.39%	3.68%	5.88%
Average	769.60	0.0189	133.30
Std. Dev.	81.10	0.0005	5.61
Coeff. of Var.	10.54%	2.42%	4.21%

Table 6: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 45$

$\Theta = 45$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	424.8618	0.0260	109.60
Std. Dev.	42.9467	0.0007	24.14
Coeff. of Var.	10.11%	2.75%	22.02%
Average	622.87	0.0249	116.57
Std. Dev.	40.36	0.0004	11.30
Coeff. of Var.	6.48%	1.50%	9.69%
Average	646.56	0.0266	123.73
Std. Dev.	65.85	0.0018	2.86
Coeff. of Var.	10.18%	6.88%	2.31%
Average	791.64	0.0253	126.37
Std. Dev.	51.23	0.0014	7.21
Coeff. of Var.	6.47%	5.43%	5.70%
Average	907.52	0.0250	121.31
Std. Dev.	63.54	0.0013	5.51
Coeff. of Var.	7.00%	5.20%	4.54%

Table 7: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 60$

$\Theta = 60$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	425.47	0.0263	109.88
Std. Dev.	17.80	0.0020	15.66
Coeff. of Var.	4.18%	7.72%	14.25%
Average	635.93	0.0276	117.06
Std. Dev.	8.36	0.0011	3.71
Coeff. of Var.	1.31%	4.15%	3.17%
Average	720.63	0.0279	114.72
Std. Dev.	30.86	0.0011	3.00
Coeff. of Var.	4.28%	4.07%	2.61%
Average	876.58	0.0286	119.20
Std. Dev.	12.22	0.0011	5.48
Coeff. of Var.	1.39%	4.00%	4.59%
Average	929.67	0.0273	119.49
Std. Dev.	43.46	0.0010	2.23
Coeff. of Var.	4.68%	3.78%	1.87%

Table 8: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 75$

$\Theta = 75$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	460.34	0.0258	90.64
Std. Dev.	8.26	0.0012	5.16
Coeff. of Var.	1.79%	4.57%	5.70%
Average	652.28	0.0274	113.86
Std. Dev.	6.70	0.0003	5.37
Coeff. of Var.	1.03%	1.07%	4.71%
Average	769.33	0.0262	100.11
Std. Dev.	23.98	0.0006	7.18
Coeff. of Var.	3.12%	2.33%	7.17%
Average	821.08	0.0277	117.52
Std. Dev.	10.56	0.0006	0.11
Coeff. of Var.	1.29%	2.08%	0.09%
Average	930.68	0.0264	114.18
Std. Dev.	21.09	0.0005	4.94
Coeff. of Var.	2.27%	1.91%	4.33%

Table 9: UD SHPB Results for $\Theta = 90$

$\Theta = 90$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	468.13	0.0282	105.75
Std. Dev.	17.00	0.0022	13.29
Coeff. of Var.	3.63%	7.69%	12.56%
Average	683.25	0.0275	103.51
Std. Dev.	38.99	0.0003	1.17
Coeff. of Var.	5.71%	1.26%	1.13%
Average	848.49	0.0263	101.59
Std. Dev.	9.69	0.0013	2.03
Coeff. of Var.	1.14%	4.78%	2.00%
Average	876.62	0.0262	109.79
Std. Dev.	34.22	0.0012	5.75
Coeff. of Var.	3.90%	4.45%	5.23%
Average	993.78	0.0249	110.75
Std. Dev.	30.95	0.0007	5.42
Coeff. of Var.	3.11%	2.79%	4.89%
Average	1058.05	0.0259	98.21
Std. Dev.	18.14	0.0004	2.70
Coeff. of Var.	1.71%	1.71%	2.75%

Table 10: XP SHPB Results for $\Theta = 0$

$\Theta = 0$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	209.10	0.0254	222.06
Std. Dev.	15.48	0.0013	2.78
Coeff. of Var.	7.40%	4.97%	1.25%
Average	412.20	0.0282	237.30
Std. Dev.	23.54	0.0022	5.57
Coeff. of Var.	5.71%	7.64%	2.35%
Average	582.40	0.0299	233.42
Std. Dev.	36.20	0.0008	6.09
Coeff. of Var.	6.22%	2.51%	2.61%
Average	729.20	0.0176	216.06
Std. Dev.	38.45	0.0061	12.62
Coeff. of Var.	5.27%	34.68%	5.84%
Average	878.60	0.0275	219.48
Std. Dev.	87.13	0.0048	13.06
Coeff. of Var.	9.92%	17.27%	5.95%

Table 11: XP SHPB Results for $\Theta = 15$

$\Theta = 15$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	385.40	0.0239	173.40
Std. Dev.	41.26	0.0038	12.97
Coeff. of Var.	10.71%	15.84%	7.48%
Average	641.20	0.0265	176.20
Std. Dev.	44.49	0.0045	12.11
Coeff. of Var.	6.94%	16.95%	6.87%
Average	846.80	0.0246	186.60
Std. Dev.	36.36	0.0063	8.79
Coeff. of Var.	4.29%	25.50%	4.71%
Average	1053.80	0.0215	226.20
Std. Dev.	74.74	0.0002	49.73
Coeff. of Var.	7.09%	0.78%	21.99%

Table 12: XP SHPB Results for $\Theta = 30$

$\Theta = 30$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	378.40	0.0373	154.40
Std. Dev.	28.18	0.0018	21.94
Coeff. of Var.	7.45%	4.95%	14.21%
Average	687.20	0.0340	156.40
Std. Dev.	41.47	0.0056	9.32
Coeff. of Var.	6.03%	16.42%	5.96%
Average	969.40	0.0330	155.60
Std. Dev.	39.42	0.0050	36.99
Coeff. of Var.	4.07%	15.11%	23.77%
Average	1140.20	0.0272	156.00
Std. Dev.	54.98	0.0023	12.21
Coeff. of Var.	4.82%	8.38%	7.82%

Table 13: XP SHPB Results for $\Theta = 45$

$\Theta = 45$ deg. (from 1-dir)	Strain Rate at Failure (/sec)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)
Average	407.20	0.0366	136.00
Std. Dev.	24.84	0.0020	7.97
Coeff. of Var.	6.10%	5.37%	5.86%
Average	731.00	0.0421	132.80
Std. Dev.	27.18	0.0012	12.38
Coeff. of Var.	3.72%	2.77%	9.32%
Average	961.00	0.0293	141.00
Std. Dev.	58.56	0.0106	14.75
Coeff. of Var.	6.09%	36.17%	10.46%
Average	1139.40	0.0266	139.40
Std. Dev.	72.90	0.0024	9.18
Coeff. of Var.	6.40%	9.02%	6.59%

For the UD material, the above data are plotted in Figs. 2 and 3. Fig. 2 plots the average ultimate stress versus Θ for several groupings of strain rates. It is seen that the quasi-static results for this paper are significantly lower (14% and 35% lower for the 1- and 2-directions respectively) than the published values. All of the data does show the typical and expected reduction in ultimate stress with increasing off-axis angle. The dynamic data also shows an increase in ultimate stress with increasing strain rate for the 1-direction (except for the group

at approximately 550 /sec), but with a larger fall-off in stress with increasing off-axis angle. For $\Theta > 45$ degrees, all data tends to similar values.

Figure 2: UD Average Ultimate Stress vs. Fiber Direction and Strain Rate

Fig. 3 plots the average ultimate strain versus Θ for several groupings of strain rates for the UD material. Except for the 1-direction results for the 400 /sec and 550 /sec groups, there does not seem to be a significant influence of strain rate on ultimate strain. Due to the relatively small number of samples at each test condition, it is difficult to determine whether the differences shown in the 400 /sec and 550 /sec groups are real effects or just statistical variances. Overall, this format for presentation of both the stress and strain results is not completely satisfactory as, within each of the strain rate “groups”, there is a significant variation in strain rate with Θ . However, due to limitations in the plotting program, plotting the stress and strain versus both off-axis angle and the distinct strain rate for each point was not possible.

For the XP material, Figs. 4 and 5 show that the ultimate stresses and strains of this composite are also sensitive to Θ . The ultimate stress is shown to decrease as the off-axis angle is increased to $\Theta = 45$. Fig. 4 also shows that the ultimate stress of the material becomes strain rate insensitive as the off-axis testing angle is increased. Fig. 5 shows that the ultimate strain values tend to increase for $15 < \Theta < 45$ for all strain rates. The ultimate strain of the material in the XP composite tends to be more strain sensitive at the larger off-axis testing angles, but no clear trend is evident. In both Figs. 4 and 5, the data plotted for $\Theta > 45$ is just a reflection of that for $\Theta < 45$ due to the symmetry of the material.

Figure 3: UD Average Ultimate Strain vs. Fiber Direction and Strain Rate

Figure 4: XP Average Ultimate Stress vs. Fiber Direction and Strain Rate

Figure 5: XP Average Ultimate Strain vs. Fiber Direction and Strain Rate

CONCLUSIONS

As expected, changing the fiber orientation angle with respect to the test direction changes the values of the ultimate stress and strain of the K-49/3501-6 KEVLAR®/Epoxy composites. Increasing the off-axis angle reduces the reinforcing effectiveness of the fiber, decreasing the composite's ultimate stress and increasing the failure strain. This effect is mitigated somewhat in the XP laminate due to more isotropic nature inherent in an XP lay-up.

The lay-up of the material influences the resulting material properties. While the UD material is stronger in the 1-direction than the XP material (~300 MPa compared to ~220 MPa), the XP material's ultimate stress suffers less of a reduction as the off-axis angle is increased. The UD material decreases from a stress of ~300 MPa at $\Theta = 0$ degrees to a stress of ~120 MPa at $\Theta = 45$ degrees, a reduction of 60%. The XP material decreases from a stress of ~220 MPa at $\Theta = 0$ degrees to a stress of ~135 MPa at $\Theta = 45$ degrees, a reduction of only 40%. Additionally, while the UD ultimate stress remains essentially constant for $\Theta > 45$ degrees, the XP ultimate stress returns to the higher values for $\Theta > 45$ degrees.

The results seem to indicate that, in compression, the KEVLAR® fiber is possibly strain rate sensitive, but that the 3501-6 epoxy matrix is not. This is supported by the result that, for both the UD and XP material, tests for the 1-direction show a noticeable increase in ultimate stress with increasing strain rate, but with a rapid return to the nominal quasi-static values for $\Theta \geq 15$ degrees.

The ultimate failure strain for both the UD and the XP material seem to be strain rate insensitive. At $\Theta = 45$ degrees, the XP material does show a significant amount of variation in the data, but the small statistical database makes it difficult to determine whether this is just data scatter or a material effect.

The statistical correlation of the data is very good, despite the small number of individual tests within each test series. This is shown by the fact that for ultimate stress, in a total of 65 test series performed for this research, 34 have coefficients of variation under 5%, 24 have

coefficients of variation between 5% and 10%, three have coefficients of variation between 10% and 20%, and only four have coefficients of variation greater than 20%

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